

PHILOLOGY

THE DIFFERENT USES OF ARTICLES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to discuss to a number of determiners from the point of view of their semantic content and how they are employed at the level of the text. It is well known that Japanese is an articleless language. Such an explanation would help us emphasize the structure of the Noun Phrase in English, in which definiteness is mainly represented by articles so that we can find similar functions in Japanese and conclude that there are heterogenous items in articleless languages that help convey the definite interpretation. As a matter of fact, I will present a classification of definite and indefinite articles, together with their semantic referentiality at the level of the text, and then I will take into consideration other categories like demonstratives, which contain deictic information and which help rendering the definite interpretation valid in English, as well as in Japanese

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1.2. Uses of the Articles

In terms of difference, the dichotomy *definite/indefinite* article can be illustrated through the functions they represent at the level of discourse and syntax together with their employment within the sentence. According to Huddleston&Pullum (2002), the semantic differentiation between focality and non-focality for elements in a discourse is represented by the indefinite article and is generally employed as a numeral. Definite articles have generic (32a), epiphoric (32b), and anaphoric (32c) values within clauses in English, together with specific structures (32d) (proper names, nominalized adjectives)

(32) (a). *The rooster* is a singing bird.

(b). *The window* of the hut was shut.

(c). I didn't refer to *the woman*.

(d). *The Carpathians, The Black Sea; The illiterate etc.*

Another criterion which differentiates syntactically between definite/indefinite articles is that the indefinite article is incompatible with certain modifying constituents of the English NP. Among these are *superlatives*, and determiners *only, same, first* and *next*.

1.2.1. The Indefinite Article

Singular indefinite noun phrases have several basic uses (Jacobs, 1995: 109): (33)

a. A specific entity with which the addressee is not familiar yet and the Noun Phrase does not uniquely identify it is referred to as the *specific indefinite employment of articles*

1. *Tom cut an old tree with yellow flowers.*

2. *A famous businessman helped his employees.*

b. A class of entities is usually denominated as the generic indefinite use of articles:

3. *Tom searched for a four-bedroom flat.*

4. *A fast helicopter is sought after by the Intelligence.*

c. A special case of the generic indefinite article provides a classification and is dealt with as the generic predicate noun phrase:

5. *Ginger was a tabby cat.*

6. *Bucharest is a heavily populated city.*

1.2.2. The Definite Article

English employs the definite article *the* almost in an universal manner with most NPs –singular or plural, countable or uncount (proper nouns are an exception). Speakers usually employ it when an entity identifiable by the addressee is indicated by the Noun Phrase. According to Jacobs (1995:110) there are a number of criteria by means of which an entity becomes identifiable, and, as a matter of fact, turns into a definite NP:

a. The contextual reference is a corollary of the immediate identifiable circumstance.

b. Entity or event is unique and has only a singular occurrence, at least in our known universe, e.g., *the moon, the Earth*.

c. For a number of reasons the entity is peculiar to a certain Universe:

- in the context of science, one can talk about *the mitochondria, the neutron*, etc.

- in the context of a anatomy, one can talk about *the heart, the arm*, etc.

- in the context of a school, one can talk about *the professor, the student*, etc.

- in the context of a written body of work (books, compositions etc.), one can talk about *the beginning, the middle, and the end*.

- in the context of 3D shaped objects in immediate location, one can talk about *the rear, the front, the left-hand side, the interior, the exterior*.

d. Anaphoricity which introduces an already known entity: *An elegant gentleman appeared on the scene. The jury offered him the Oscar.*

e. Superlatives describe a number of entities as unique through the employment of modifiers: *longest, most courageous, least important*, or through quantifiers designating uniqueness, such as *only* and *sole* in *the only computer* and *the sole purpose*.

f. A number of semantic determiners describe the entity as present at the time of the utterance or in proximity, e.g., *the red glove, the guy over the park*.

g. A Noun Phrase consisting of a noun designated with a specific reference and is determined by a relative, as in *the anger that he felt*.

The grammatical system of English allows the definite and indefinite article to be mutually exclusive, even though they complete each other. Their semantic roles are complementary in a clause. In (35a) anaphoricity plays a role in specifying the noun, while in (35b) the noun is not mandatory to be specified.

(35) (a) *He's the chosen.*

(b) *He's a chosen.*

The notion of definiteness encompasses a larger domain and is not restricted only to articles since its range of variation in relation to definite expressions includes other related grammatical phenomena: demonstratives, possessives, personal pronouns. Some of these are definite determiners, differing from *the* in that they combine definiteness with some other semantic content which can account by itself for the definite interpretation. We should follow Lyons' (2003) classification which suggests the existence of *simple definites/indefinites* to describe Noun Phrases with *the* or *a* (to which he ascribes the feature [+Def] or [-Def]), and complex definites/indefinites in which [+Def] is present as a consequence of, or otherwise in combination with another feature.

1.2.3. The Demonstratives

Kaplan (1989) ascribes demonstratives two roles. First, reference is highly involved in that the canonical employment of demonstratives is connected to the context (Roberts's (2002) and has extralinguistic dimension. Second, they own *prepositional content*. Researchers like Wolter (2003) pointed out there is not much difference between NPs and the behaviour of demonstratives. The most prominent classes of demonstratives are deictic (36a), anaphoric (36b) and explicit demonstratives (Wolter's paradigm) (36c):

(36) (a) (Pointing at Clark) That guy is intelligent.

(b) A cat_i lives upstairs. That cat_i starts meowing when owner leaves.

(c) [That hero]_i[who killed the dragon]_i[will inherit half the kingdom.]

(Wolter, 2003:2)

Emotive demonstratives are characterized by the requirement of salience since they behave like anaphors in that the entity must have already been discussed. According to Lakoff (1974) *emotional solidarity* with interlocutors is in their semantic content.

(37) *That* Gray Gandalf is a wise gentleman!

Some argue that demonstratives are distinguished from the definite article in that they contain a deictic element like in (37). Authors endeavored to find a selective criterion in their structure. J. Lyons (1975, 1977) and Sommerstein (1972) assume that there is a spatial implicature that distinguishes *this* and *that* from *the*. Anderson and Keenan (1985:67) agree on this perspective and argue that a demonstrative system with a singular item would not look much different from the employment of definite articles.

Demonstratives *this/these* and *that/those* can function as a complete NP or as a determiner in slot (c) (Heim, 1982:45). No substantial difference in meaning

can sometimes be observed when demonstratives are employed as determiners and may be substituted by the definite article.

The interpretation of definiteness in the form of demonstratives does not rely on the criterion of inclusiveness, even though most authors argue that demonstratives are generally definite in nature. What might set them apart is the actual referent might be in semantic contrast with other potential referents, since the demonstrative reference is clear or implied. (Hawkins: 1978). Identifiability is the common link between demonstratives and definite articles and the reference becomes clearly implied as in *Give me that spell*.

Demonstratives roll around two kinds of anaphoric function – substitution anaphora and textual anaphora, both of which are intricately explained by a number of researchers like Dixon (2003:38).

A.Substitution Anaphora: A full NP is substituted by the anaphoric NP, and the anaphoric constituent repeats it in place. More precisely, a demonstrative in slot (c), with substitution anaphoric function, might usually be replaced with the definite article:

(38) (a) He wins more money, but *that/this salary* is not sufficient.

(b) She gave birth on Monday and (on) *that morning* they argued heavily.

B.Textual Anaphora: it introduces a proposition mostly in the form of a clause or even a lengthy piece of discourse and is referred to by a NP with a demonstrative. Examples:

(39) (a) He argues excessively and *for that* (reason) Anna hates him.

(b) He doesn't exercise and *this* (behaviour) threatens Mary.

In the textual anaphoric case, the definite article may not be replaced with a demonstrative. Something larger in extent than an NP is required to be specified by a deictic determiner. Deixis comes as the main criterion linking definite articles with demonstratives (*This/(the) robe comes in handy. Whom did you sell that/(the) falt to?*).

A semantic value not peculiar to the definite article, but to the demonstrative *that* is as an intensifier with adjective or adverb (Jespersen, 1933:50) The appropriate contextual reference introduces emotional semantic content as a derogatory overtone:

(40) I hate *that* Smith John, the all knowing magician.

1.3. Conclusions of This Section

The main methods to express definiteness in English are through the employment of definite and indefinite articles and through the usage of demonstratives along with possessives. Unlike Japanese, English has the advantage that both Number is expressed through the employment of plural marker *-s* while Gender is not overtly expressed just like in Japanese. Definiteness can be dealt with in terms of uniqueness and familiarity as logic forms that derive from contextual reference. We bring into discussion the importance of context for English, even though it is not a necessary topic due to the presence of articles, because in Japanese the definite interpretation of a NP resides mostly on anaphoricity

and cataphoricity of the contextual reference within different clauses. This does not mean that Japanese resorts only to ambiguous processes like contextual reference, as we will see in the next chapters.

The difference between definite and indefinite interpretations for English NPs brings into discussion one of the major characteristics of English nouns, namely that they are inherently non-definite, unlike Japanese, which has been shown, through null-NPs to possess inherently definite nouns, even though the demonstration is still highly debatable in the literature. The previous observation is supported by the fact that the indefinite character of a noun in English is overtly marked, that is, through the employment of an indefinite article, which means that nouns must represent a different nature in terms of definiteness, other than that of the dichotomy definite/indefinite and that is the tertiary non-definite nature.

One argument comes from the idea that nouns in English cannot be grammatical in their lexicon status, more specifically, they cannot occur in sentences in their non-definite nature. What distinguishes *the* from *a/an* is uniqueness –the existence of an entity meeting the descriptive content of the NP. While the use of an

indefinite description in a simple, sentence merely asserts the existence of an entity, the use of a definite description asserts in addition its uniqueness in that regard. Familiarity, on the other hand, comes hand in hand with the uniqueness criterion in that it presents the entity described as part of the universe of the observer, unlike uniqueness which presents the object as part of the general universe. Unlike definiteness, which is a syntactic notion that can be demonstrated through diagrams, uniqueness and familiarity are essentially semantic and point out to the content of a noun.

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